

THE PATHWAYS TO CONSTITUTIONAL REFORMS IN NIGERIA; THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE GRADUAL APPROACH

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Abstract

Constitutional reform is a major proponent of Federalism. Nigeria as a country operates a federal system of government and constitutional reforms need to happen at a point in time. The failure of the 2014 National Conference has shown how ineffective the mega constitutional approach is in Nigeria. Indeed, the North-South division has practically become a key element in the constitutional reform of Nigeria's present constitutional policy, with the North favouring the continuing of today's centred integrationist federalism, and the South demanding significant constitutional decentralization. Therefore, this paper will pitch its argument toward a gradual approach focusing on the incremental constitutional amendment, legislative supplementation and judicial mediation as against the mega-constitutional approach to be sufficient for the Nigeria Federal system.

Keywords: The Constitution; reforms; Federalism; mega-constitutional approach; a gradual approach

1. INTRODUCTION

Constitutional reform is a major proponent of Federalism. Nigeria as a country operates a Federal system of government and constitutional reforms need to happen at a point in time. The 1999 Nigerian Constitution has been considered by many Nigerians to be military-centric and the constitutional expression that "We are the People" doesn't reflect a constitution sanctioned by the Nigerian populace; thereby leading to advocacy and agitations from various actors about a radical change in the Constitution. Since the transitioning of Nigeria from military rule to civilian rule in May 1999, there have been strong constitutional protests for altering the central confederation that the military left behind in the 1999 Constitution. During this timeframe, the government, community or ethnic-regional bodies have been discussing the constitutional restructuring agenda, establishing professional constitutional review bodies, convening nationwide constitutional conferences or public hearings, ratifying constitutional amendments, or setting in motion inclusive legislative drafting or agreements. (Suberu, 2015). Unfortunately, no success has been made in attempts for these reforms. However, the National Assembly is given another shot at constitutional change.

Furthermore, there have been various arguments from scholars on the kind of constitutional reforms that are appropriate for the Nigeria Federal system. A school of thought is in support of a mega-constitutional approach while the other is in support of a gradual approach. Therefore, this paper will pitch its argument toward a gradual approach focusing on the incremental constitutional amendment, legislative supplementation

and judicial arbitration as against the mega-constitutional approach to be sufficient for the Nigeria Federal system.

2. CONSTITUTIONAL REFORM DEMANDS

Like every other country that operates a Federal system, Nigeria runs a rigid constitution. The amendments of the Constitution under the rigid system calls for two-thirds of the majority in the National Assembly's two chambers. Likewise, the amendment demands that no less than two-thirds of all 36 states in the federation be approved by a resolution by subnational legislatures. Such rigour is more stringent about matters concerning the federation's restructuring and citizens' basic rights. (Okpanachi & Garba, 2010). Therefore, making it difficult for a mega-constitutional approach in terms of reforms.

Before the military government took over governance in 1966, a Federal legislative system was operated by Nigeria with the Hausa-Fulani, Ibo and Yoruba being the dominant tribes occupying an unequal region in the North, East and West respectively. Every region had its constitutions, local government systems, local police, autonomous revenue, the independent judiciary and regional political parties. (Suberu, 2015). Unfortunately, this led to ethnopolitical instability and motivated various coups perpetrated by the military. In response to this tension, the military implemented a centralized system of the government putting all functionally within their grasp. Though, this succession ensured that only the northern military leaders were dominating administrative duties thereby creating local-level conflicts that have led to a

high tension of the north-south divide over the federal distribution of power and resources.

Indeed, the North-South division has practically become a key element in the constitutional reform of Nigeria's present constitutional policy, with the North favouring the continuing of today's centred integrationist federalism, and the South demanding significant constitutional decentralization.

This is evident in the demands and proposals from various groups such as the southern-based ethnic establishments in their debate for a review in the 1999 Constitution and clamour for the restructuring of Nigeria into a decentralized federation. (Pronaco, 2007). The Pronaco design expresses the idea of major Southern Nigerian thinkers to "the general purpose of restructuring is the independence of ethnic nationalities with a limited national government coordinating a federal union" (Adamolekun, 2005, 401). Consequently, the Northern region denounced the SNC ideology and termed it as chaos, disorder and political instability. They also denied the idea that true federalism is a "negligent assault on the very basis of our continuing reality as a nation," while "declaring the sacrosanct unity of Nigeria" and recognizing effective dogmatic guidance as to the solution for Nigeria's political problems, rather than fundamental constitutional reform. Rather they are in support of maintaining the present 36-state system and advocating the direct federal support of locals and their independence from states in terms of politics and finance, thereby leading to a balanced development of Nigeria.

3. PATHWAYS TO CONSTITUTIONAL REFORMS

The failure of the 2014 National Conference has shown how ineffective the mega constitutional approach is in Nigeria. With Nigerian experience, a comprehensive 1999 Constitution restructuring or amendment 1999 is unachievable but also unwanted (due to the absence of support for the notion in north Nigeria). This is because the 1999 federal constitutional system, with all its shortcomings, has certain characteristics which are truly institutionally sound and probably generally valid. As the Constitution contains multiple constituents, fragmentation into several states of each major ethnic group; prohibition of open sectional parties; establishing federal or ethnic power-sharing rules based upon the consociation style; and equipment of the national government to promote national integration with sufficient powers and resources. Therefore, constitutional reforms are achievable and positive when focused on the creativity of renewal and slow implementation with some of these approaches.

Incremental Constitutional Approach

Constitutional amendments from 2010–2011 have proved that Nigeria may implement formal constitutional changes using a disconnected, fragmented, or gradual approach to political reforms rather than a mega-constitutional strategy. An issue to look into will be the electoral reforms. The electoral system has failed to elect leaders in free and fair circumstances because of poor leadership, thereby making elections in Nigeria a matter of "vote without choice" spectacle. Consequently, electoral changes are needed, if the federal rule is to advance the

country, for these reforms can lead to the possibilities for political decentralization being broadened through more competitive and mixed national and sub-national election outcomes, judicial independence and confidence and a genuinely democratic basis for Nigerian Federalism.

There is progress as steps are taken towards this direction. President Yar'Adua has strongly criticised the bogus elections that elected him to office and established an Electoral Reform Committee (ERC) to recommend solutions for restoring the sanctuary of a ballot box. Justice Muhammed Lawal Uwais, who retired as Chief Justice of the Federation was announced by the President in August 2007 as chairman of the ERC. In December 2008, the Committee presented its findings to the President. The report contains extensive measures such as rejecting the running of the electoral committee by the Presidency and guaranteeing that disagreements emerging from this are fairly and promptly resolved. The Committee proposed the adoption of three proposals to provide practical substance for reforms. There was a draft amendment to the 1999 Constitution as the first proposal. The second is the Electoral Act 2006 amendment bill and the third is the Electoral Offences Commission bill. (Okpanachi & Garba, 2010). The former chairman of the Transition Monitoring Group (TMG) and ERC member, Mr Festus Okoye once stated that the logical way will be to concentrate on electoral reforms and leave the sensitive questions of federalism, if followed, probably ruin everything like in the past.

Legislative Supplementation

Another approach worth pursuing is the Legislative supplementation which Nigeria can utilise in achieving federal governance reforms without resorting to an official constitutional reform plan is high-profile, costly, and inevitably controversial. This is achievable as Section 303 of the Constitution of 1999 gives the National Assembly jurisdiction to act on the administrative and political framework of Abuja, thereby ensuring the decision process is a legislative injunction and not a constitutional battle. Likewise, the 1999 Constitution, paragraph 162, gives the National Assembly powers to prescribe the federal income-sharing "terms and ... manner", subject to certain provisions, with an inclusion of 13% minimum derivation rule and recognition of "the allocation principles . . . of population, equality of states, internal revenue generation, landmass, terrain as well as population density" (Federal Republic of Nigeria Constitution, 1999). This constitutional right was invoked by the National Assembly in 2004 when the use of the derivation rule was activated in alleviating the tension in Nigeria over the resource control of offshore oil revenue.

Judicial Mediation

The Supreme Court of Nigeria since 1999 judged a series of federal-state disputes over income allocation, local governance, public order and electoral policies which, even in the absence of major constitutional amendments, significantly contributed to the development and renewal of the Nigerian federation. Some decisions were taken by the courts to illustrate the continuity roles and challenges of Federalism. In 2007, in regards to the general elections, the petitions filed reached 1250 (INEC 2007), this was the highest number obtained compared to 527 in 2003 general

elections. (The Punch, 10 February 2009). The way Nigeria Judiciary handled the petitions is worth noting, enshrining the tenets of democracy. In *Kayode Fayemi vs Segun Oni* (2007), the election was won by PDP according to the results announced by INEC, Kayode Fayemi opposed the results and challenged it before the Ekiti State Elections Petitions Tribunal (ESEPT). After losing his appeal at the ESEPT, Fayemi appealed to the CofA in Ilorin. In February 2009, the court upheld his complaints, which was enough to nullify the election of the PDP's Segun Oni. (Enweremadu 2009).

There have been successes and failures of the Nigeria Judiciary in the arbitration of legal cases in the country but the court can contribute immensely to the progress of the Nigeria Federal System of Government.

4. CONCLUSION

History has demonstrated that only seldomly can the mega-constitutional approach work. This applies to the Nigerian federalism transformation as well. Experience showed that reforming the constitutions and constitutional amendments is no simple feat in profoundly divided nations. The lessons drawn from failure in constitutional arrangements propose that mega constitutional reforms, with their intrinsic inclination to extend the plan to encompass multiple group requests, may undermine good governance and prospects of resolution by starting the constitutional processes to massive tacit support through public opinions. Moreover, the existing issues of the federation might be exacerbated rather than mitigated by some of the suggestions linked with the mega-constitutional reform agenda. Apart from this, in matters that demand constitutional scrutiny, Nigerian political elites seldom choose correct approaches. Rather, the process has been marked by political conspiracies, personal goals that have been overridden, manoeuvres by the aristocrats who have scampered the whole constitutional exercises. Thus, there is no evidence to support that these approaches are going to be smooth sailing, for as promising as legislative supplementation, judicial mediation and incremental constitutional approach (starting with electoral reforms, where citizens can make significant preferences select their leaders and therefore strengthen their ability to take influential part in the decision-making by the government which affects their lives). It is advisable to adopt this than the mega-constitutional approach. Yet, it is worth pursuing a path as it is more hopeful than the mega-constitutional approach. Likewise, it provides civil societies with an ample opportunity to a broader base to better argue for development over regional and parochial interests.

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